

THE ROLE OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL METHODS IN ACCELERATING TISSUE REGENERATION IN PATIENTS WITH CRITICAL LOWER LIMB ISCHEMIA

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The global number of patients with new diabetic foot ulcers increases annually. Circulatory disorders lead to neuro- and microangiopathies, which play a significant role in the pathogenesis of the diabetic foot syndrome, posing a direct threat or contributing to the development of ulcerative necrotic processes and foot gangrene. The prevalence of diabetes continues to rise worldwide, and according to the International Diabetes Federation, in 2021, 537 million adults aged 20 to 79 were living with diabetes globally, with the incidence of foot ulcer defects reaching up to 50% among them (Dedov I.I., 2013).

In Russia, 20% to 50% of all diabetes-related hospitalizations are associated with foot lesions. The risk of lower limb amputations is also higher in this patient category, accounting for 50% to 80% of all non-traumatic amputations. Therefore, the development of modern methods for a comprehensive approach to the treatment of patients with this pathology is relevant today, focusing on organ-preserving surgeries and preventing postoperative complications. Postoperative complications after lower limb amputations are observed in 64% of patients, with an average hospital stay of 58.2–65.7 days, and for every second patient, life expectancy after surgery does not exceed 2 years. One of the most severe complications of diabetes mellitus (DM) is lower limb damage, leading to purulent necrotic processes on the foot in 6–15% of patients (M.D. Dibirov et al., 2021).

The issue of choosing the method for treating purulent necrotic lesions in diabetic foot syndrome complicated by severe critical ischemia remains unresolved. Currently, there is limited clinical information on the role and application of an abacterial medium using electroactivated solutions (EAS) in the prevention and treatment of purulent-necrotic lesions of the lower limbs in diabetic foot syndrome complicated by critical lower limb ischemia.

Purpose of the study: To improve the outcomes of treating patients with diabetic foot syndrome (DFS) and critical lower limb ischemia through the use of endovascular interventions and an improved method of ultrasonic wound treatment (UWT).

Materials and Methods: This study is based on the examination and treatment data of 123 patients with critical lower limb ischemia in diabetic foot syndrome complicated by purulent wounds (Wagner grades III–V, 1979), who

received inpatient treatment at the clinical base of the Bukhara State Medical Institute between 2021 and 2024.

According to the study objectives, all patients were conditionally divided into two major groups. The comparison group (Group I) included 46 patients (37.4%) with critical lower limb ischemia in DFS who underwent a traditional method of local treatment. This included: angiographic examination, endovascular intervention, and local surgical treatment combined with ultrasonic wound treatment (UWT) using physiological saline.

In contrast, 77 patients (66.2%) in Group II received UWT using a 25% chemical solution of dimexide and a physical solution of electroactivated solution (EAS). Based on the study objectives, Group II was further divided into two subgroups:

- Subgroup II-A included 37 patients (48.1%) with DFS and critical lower limb ischemia complicated by purulent wounds. These patients received UWT using a 25% solution of dimexide.
- Subgroup II-B included 40 patients (51.9%) with the same diagnosis who received UWT using a combination of 25% dimexide solution and EAS-A.

All patients in Groups I and II underwent emergency surgery on the day of admission to open the purulent focus and sanitize the cavity with a 3% antiseptic hydrogen peroxide solution. After drying, UWT was performed using the respective solutions for each group. In the second phase of wound progression, UWT was discontinued, and sanitation was performed using the electroactivated catholyte solution (EAS-C). The wounds were treated with Levomekol ointment and dressings soaked with an anolyte solution in combination with a 25% dimexide solution. Dressings were changed once daily.

Research Results: The study evaluated the effectiveness of traditional treatment for DFS in patients with critical lower limb ischemia (Group I, n=46). Diagnosis included angiographic examinations and duplex scanning of vessels, which revealed significant stenoses and occlusions at various arterial levels. Treatment included local UWT, intensive insulin therapy, antibacterial treatment, symptomatic support, and endovascular procedures (balloon angioplasty and stenting). Intervention strategies were based on the anatomical and functional condition of the vessels according to the levels of damage (I–III).

Against the background of combined conservative and surgical treatment, positive dynamics in laboratory and clinical indicators were observed: decreased body temperature, leukocytosis, MSM levels, LII, and ESR. However, in cases of

late presentation and severe ischemia (Wagner grades IV–V), some patients required amputations at various levels: 21.7% — at the lower leg, 25% — atypical foot resections, 33.9% — toe amputations. Mortality was 6.5% (3 patients) and was associated with severe multiple organ failure and delayed hospitalization.

The study also included 40 patients with severe DFS complicated by purulent-necrotic lesions (per Wagner classification) and diagnosed critical lower limb ischemia. All received comprehensive treatment including intensive insulin therapy, metabolic correction, angiographic examinations, and endovascular interventions when indicated. Locally, UWT was performed using a 25% dimexide solution combined with EAS-A.

The results showed significantly better dynamics compared to the previous subgroup: faster reduction in intoxication indicators, improvement in regional blood flow, and glycemia levels. Average body temperature normalized by day 7, and leukocyte levels and other markers of intoxication (MSM, LII, ESR) decreased more rapidly than in the comparison group. The frequency of major amputations decreased, while organ-preserving procedures (necrosectomies, toe amputations) increased. Mortality was 2.5%, and the average hospital stay was 8.3 ± 1.2 days. Thus, the combined method of UWT with dimexide and EAS-A improves treatment outcomes and prognosis in patients with severe DFS.

Conclusion: The data confirm the importance of early diagnosis, a multidisciplinary approach, and modern vascular reconstruction methods in the treatment of purulent-necrotic forms of DFS with critical ischemia.

Incorporating electroactivated solution into the UWT protocol significantly improved clinical outcomes: it accelerated wound cleansing, reduced complication rates, and increased survival. This combined approach may be considered a promising direction in the treatment of purulent-necrotic complications of diabetic foot syndrome.